

The impact of the Ukrainian refugee crisis on the security dimension in Romania during 2022-2023

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Abstract

The European Union and its Member States are currently facing an unprecedented migration phenomenon, a refugee crisis in Ukraine triggered by the Russian Federation's military invasion of Ukraine that began in February 2022. This ongoing military conflict has created the biggest humanitarian crisis in modern European history, resulting in many casualties and population movements outside Ukraine's borders. Although we believe that the institutions of the European Union have previously managed a similar event, the Syrian refugee crisis, in an effective way, the current refugee crisis, the second one in the last ten years, shows that international migration should be seen from the perspective of a threat to European security, quickly becoming one of the main issues, and certainly one of the most contested, in current times. The objective of our paper is to analyze the relationship between migration and security and to examine the impact that the refugee crisis in Ukraine has on the dimensions of security in Romania.

Keywords

migration; refugees; policies; security; political crisis

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Introduction

The objective of this research is to present a significant topic in the present context, namely the European Union's efforts to ensure security in the context of a new wave of international migration resulting from a recent military conflict: the Ukrainian refugee crisis of 2022. European security has previously been confronted with this type of threat over the past eight years, in the context of two comparable phenomena: the Syrian refugee crisis of 2015 and the Afghan refugee crisis of 2021. The three migration events are quite similar if one were to classify them according to the causes that led to immigration into the European Union. Conversely, these crises are distinguished by the magnitude of the phenomenon, the number of individuals entering the EU, and how they are dealt with by European decision-making institutions. Given the frequency of these refugee crises, migration continues to represent a significant challenge for the European Union. The considerable influx of migrants and refugees into the European region necessitates a novel approach, as this recent wave of immigration has significantly affected the dimensions of European security and had direct consequences on the security sectors in Romania.

This wave of migration could be classified as one of the largest, with approximately 8.2 million refugees reaching the European space (Centre for Research and Analysis of Migration, 2023). Considering it to be a type of irregular migration in terms of its development, we propose through this study to address the connection between migration and security. Starting from an observation confirmed by previous studies on migration waves and refugee crises in the European Union, namely that migration is an important source of insecurity, one that is recognized as a security problem in the member states of the European Union, this article aims to answer the following question: What was the impact of the Ukrainian refugee crisis on the security dimension in Romania in the 2022-2023 period?

Focusing on the effects these waves of refugees have created on security sectors, in this study we aim to identify concretely what was the response offered by the Romanian authorities to this humanitarian crisis in 2022 and to analyze what are the consequences of this crisis on the economic, political, societal, and military security in Romania. To carry out the impact analysis on Romania's security dimensions, we will use a qualitative analysis of official data, provided by the Government of Romania, the Strategic Coordination and Humanitarian Assistance Group, and the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR).

Although the migration literature contains a wealth of studies on waves of migrants and refugees who choose the European Union as a destination, most of the previous research deals with topics such as migration securitization or the effects of migration on the societal security dimension. In this respect, the analysis of the impact of the Ukrainian refugee crisis on Romania's security dimensions developed in this article contributes to the literature by presenting how a threat to particular dimension can propagate to other dimensions as well, suggesting it is essential to analyse this migratory phenomenon from a multidimensional perspective, as indicated in the new security analysis framework proposed by Buzan and Waever (2003).

Migration and security

The concepts of migration and security are two complex and interconnected phenomena that have become increasingly relevant in the context of the continuous development of the globalization phenomenon. At the same time, they are also relevant in the current geopolitical context on the international stage, in which the political situation in certain states is critical and conflictual. In recent decades, migration to the European Union and its member states has become a significant global

phenomenon, with the European Union serving as the primary destination for migrants from diverse continents. This irregular migration has resulted in the emergence of numerous challenges and threats to the national and human security of European Union member states.

To understand the effects of migration on security, we will provide a brief overview of the phenomenon. Migration is one of the oldest social phenomena in the world, remaining one of the main topics of discussion and even the main security problem faced by states in the current period. Buzan and Weaver state that migration has been a security issue since ancient times, when Greece and Rome emerged and disappeared as states because of it (Buzan & Waever, 2003: 23). Migration, through the different forms it can take – illegal, forced, irregular, or irregular – can be regarded as a threat to national security, to society, and, implicitly, to the existential security of the individual, threatening the identity of a society through a change in its composition.

Conceptualizing migration. According to researchers in the field of population studies, migration is a main characteristic of human beings, which has had a significant role throughout history in the emergence of states and in the formation of new global configurations. Moreover, it contributed “to the growth of the world economy, to the evolution of states and societies, including the enrichment of cultures and civilizations” (Pescaru, 2014: 189). Looking from this perspective, the migration phenomenon has created social, economic, and political changes, being influenced to a high extent by globalization.

After consulting the specialized literature that offers evolutionary perspectives on migration (Tudorache, 2006: 95-100) and the reports on the migration phenomenon made available by the International Organization for Migration in recent years, we find that the migration phenomenon is not a random process that takes place only in a certain temporal period and geographical area. Referring to the forms of migration, the causes, and the intensity of the migration population process, we can say that its manifestation is different from case to case, and political, economic and security factors are those that influence and accentuate it.

Etymologically, the concept of migration comes from the Latin word *migratio* and is defined in a way unanimously accepted by most researchers and institutions as a human and normal activity, which represents, according to the Oxford English Dictionary, “movement of a person or group of persons from one country, locality or place of residence with a view to settling in another place”. Despite the simplicity of the dictionary definition, the concept of migration is considered to be quite ambiguous and subject to interpretations because it treats migration in a general way and it does not distinguish between the main forms that migration takes in certain contexts, where migration can be voluntary or forced, legal or illegal, creating in this sense ambiguities and overlaps between the terms immigrant and refugee. For this reason, we consider it necessary to present the definitions developed by the main institutions working in this field, together with the description of the main forms of migration, to finally identify what are the causes that generate international migration.

Viewed from a demographic perspective, migration is defined according to the strategic studies researcher as a “complex phenomenon consisting in the movement of persons from one territorial area to another, followed by a change of domicile and/or employment in a form of activity in the arrival area” (Sarcinschi, 2008: 8). However, the design of migration does not provide a clear perspective of distinguishing the movement made by migrants from a spatial point of view.

Referring to the typologies of the migration phenomenon, to distinguish the forms of migration in terms of borders, migration is defined as the voluntary movement of a person or group of people from one state to another or from one territorial area to another, following a context determined by economic, social, or political factors. Following this conceptualization that brings into

discussion the movement of population within or outside borders, the two main forms of the phenomenon are distinguished: internal migration and international migration, which target the external part of a state's borders. International migration, according to the International Organization for Migration, is the following process: the international migrant leaves his State of origin for another State, called the State of destination, with the aim of settling over a longer period. According to the International Organisation for Migration, this definition encompasses several types of migration and implicitly different types of migrants and refugees (International Organisation for Migration, 2018: 15). International migration comprises several types of migration, which are classified according to the temporal criterion, the degree of decision-making freedom of the persons involved in the process and the legal status of the migration. In this regard, in the following we will present the forms of migration according to all these criteria, as they are presented in the specialized literature.

Among the most common forms of migration are those that are distinguished according to the temporary criterion, they being, according to researchers Anghel Gabriel and Horvath Istvan, permanent migration, which involves a permanent change of residence to another state (Anghel & Horvath, 2009: 20) and temporary migration, which according to the United Nations includes "people who move from one country to another for more than three months but less than a year" (Pescaru, 2014: 189).

Going further in the process of classifying forms of migration, we distinguish according to the degree of decision-making freedom that people involved in the process have: voluntary and forced migration. Voluntary migration in recent years, globally, has taken the form of economic migration since the main reason for this form of mobility was predominantly economic. In contrast, migration is theoretically framed as forced when the decision to migrate "is taken in the context of direct or indirect pressure from persons, institutions or other external circumstances" (Anghel & Horvath, 2009: 22). This form of migration is one of the most problematic because it generally creates large dispersals of people in distress or in conflict situations. Among the most relevant and contemporary examples are the refugee crises of 2015 and the Ukrainian refugee crisis of 2022, both generated by military conflicts, which created humanitarian crises in and around Europe.

Depending on the legal status of migration achieved by persons in the process of moving to another state, we classically distinguish between legal and illegal migration. In this sense, legal migration is carried out in an organized way, in which immigrants during the process of travel "complies with all legal rigors implied by the migration process" (Anghel & Horvath, 2009: 22-24) respecting the entry measures on the territory of a state, the time granted according to the visa and including integration measures. Illegal migration is defined as "the movement of persons that takes place outside international norms, regulations and agreements, governing entry into or exit from the state of origin, transit or destination" (International Organisation for Migration, 2019: 116).

Following the discussion of all these definitions and classifications of the concept of migration, in order to not create any conceptual mistakes, we consider it essential to offer a brief definition of the concepts of migrant and refugee. From the perspective of the situation that generated the migration process, in the case of these two terms, a first distinction can be made. Refugees are people who move because of forced migration caused by potentially life-threatening aspects, while migrants are those categories of people who may be legal or illegal and who carry out the migration process on a voluntary basis.

Causes of international migration. In the twentieth century, the mobility process is no longer a problem, because people enjoy both the freedom to emigrate and immigrate, as well as the ease with which such a process can be carried out from one state to another, due to globalization. However,

the ease of carrying out this migration process has favored and accentuated the emergence of international migration flows, which have become increasingly complex and often increasingly difficult to manage and regulate.

Analyzing migration through the push-pull theory, developed by Ravenstein in 1885, and later revised by Lee, we note that the decision to migrate is influenced by rejection factors in the origin state and attraction factors in the destination state (Lee, 1996: 47-57). This theory provides a differentiation of the factors that cause people to leave their state, most of them negative, and the factors that attract migrants to a particular state, most of them positive. In general, thrust factors (push) are considered by some researchers to be decisive in choosing to migrate and are most often exemplified as those related to human safety and security, economy (economic causes), environment (when people are forced to emigrate due to natural causes) and social environment.

The main cause that has a significant role in the decision to migrate, internationally, is represented by security factors, which involve and represent essential issues related to the safety and life of people who decide to emigrate from a state. This situation often materializes in a migration process, carried out as a result of persecution and discrimination based on nationality, race, religion, or even political affiliation to different groups or, even worse, following a civil war such as the one which generated, in the case of the refugee crisis of 2015, a significant number of refugees in the states of the European Union. In 2021 another wave of refugees coming from Afghanistan at the borders of the European Union was caused by political instability in the Middle East and in 2022, as a result of the Ukrainian refugee crisis, approximately 8.2 million refugees (UNHCR Romania, 2023) applied for protection in member states of the European Union.

A second important factor influencing the decision to carry out a migration process and directly influencing international migration globally is the economic one. The cause of economic migration is mainly the precarious situation in the origin country, characterized by high unemployment rates, revealing a lack of jobs and a weak labor market. In most cases, people who emigrate come from underdeveloped or developing countries, agricultural states, and the reasons for those who emigrate are related to the rather low standard of living. The factors that attract people to immigrate are closely related to the economic situation in the destination state and to the possibility of finding a job that offers immigrants a higher source of income than the state of origin and a better life. As an example, the developed countries of the European Union in the Mediterranean area act as a pull factor for migrants from North Africa, who generally go to states such as Italy and Spain (Sawe, 2019).

Another important pushing factor influencing people's decision to emigrate is represented by environmental causes, represented by the dangers resulting from consequences that nature causes, with direct impact on human security. Among these causes we find natural disasters, such as earthquakes, tsunamis, or hurricanes, but also factors that cause hunger, lack of water or even pollution, all of which affect human security and force them, in one way or another, to migrate to other states.

The category of pushing factors can also include social factors, which, according to Tătaru, are primarily constituted by the human desire to have a high standard of living and the need to provide the family with a favorable framework to develop and live in a developed community. Most of the times, people who decide to emigrate due to these factors go to developed countries that offer a well-developed social and health system or a state with an education system that offers prospects (Tătaru, 2019: 23).

Assumptions on migration. After identifying the causes that influence international migration, we appreciate that this process will continue and will remain at least as complex because the

international environment is still dominated by political fluctuations, wars, and civil conflicts, which directly influence the factors pushing the population towards safe states. In addition to security factors, economic factors of attraction and pushing the population towards migration to better developed European states will certainly persist, all of which create and maintain debates in destination countries on migration and policies for receiving immigrants and refugees.

It can be argued that migration is a complex phenomenon that considers both the natural dynamics of population and political, economic, social, military, and environmental factors. This phenomenon is a continuous one and, as such, impossible to stop, which is why a deep knowledge of this phenomenon is needed, in order to develop capable mechanisms through which to manage it as well as possible. As mentioned, due to the complexity of the phenomenon, it must be treated from various perspectives: historical, sociological, psychological, demographic, cultural, religious, political, ideological, focusing on its implications for the functioning of migrant groups and society.

The relationship between migration and security. International relations and security theorists understood security as the feeling of security, manifested in situations where there were no threats. In the traditional conception, promoted by realist researchers, during the Cold War, security was defined as state security or national security, the state being the main object of reference (Wolfers, 1952). However, with the end of the Cold War and the emergence of non-military security threats, Copenhagen School theorists proposed a new security analysis framework through which they reconceptualized security and broadened the scope of security reference objects. Through the model proposed by them, they introduced sectoral analysis, which focused on identifying threats and assessing security measures in the military, political, societal, economic, and environmental sectors (Buzan, Weaver & de Wilde, 2011: 14).

Within the traditional perspective on the relationship between migration and security, emphasis was placed on the impact and effects that migration creates in the field of economic and political security – especially on the social side, but according to the new security analysis framework, an inter-connectivity is created between dimensions, which reveals that the impact of migration is also found in the other dimensions of security. Starting from Huysmans' statement that the concept of security can be approached both from the perspective of national security and from the perspective of human security, we believe that the relationship between migration and security is multidimensional, and migration can influence the dimensions of security in different ways. For example, mass migration flows can be considered both a threat to national security from a military perspective, because they threaten a risk to border security, and a threat to political security, because they can create destabilization of social order in a state (Huysmans, 2006).

In light of presenting the relationship between migration and security, it is essential to mention that migration cannot be considered just a security problem or a threat resulting from a conflict situation, because the relationship that is created between these two concepts is not just a unidirectional one. Consulting the historical waves of immigration in Europe, it can be argued that immigrants and refugees arriving on the territory of Europe have contributed to its reconstruction. Moreover, we notice that in the contemporary period migrants can make quite valuable contributions to the economy of European states, representing workforce.

The 2022 Ukrainian refugee crisis. The Ukrainian refugee crisis began with the Russian military invasion of Ukraine on February 24, 2022. The war waged by the invaders on Ukrainian territory, together with the shelling of civilian targets and the violence of Russian soldiers on civilians, has created one of the deepest and greatest humanitarian crises of the twenty-first century and certainly the most important of all, representing the largest foreign migration on European soil since World War

II. Since the start of the invasion, an estimated 21.9 million Ukrainians have crossed their borders into Europe with the intention of escaping the war and finding a safe place to live, at least for a while. Of these, according to UNHCR statistics, 13 million returned to their own country after the conflict in western and central Ukraine improved. Although the situation has improved even more in some areas, and the Ukrainian army began to recover some of the occupied territories in the Spring of 2023, approximately 8.2 million Ukrainians are still registered with the refugee status in member states of the European Union. In addition to the refugee crisis generated by the war in Syria, Ukrainian migrants have also planned to reach the more developed countries of the European Union, most of them registered as refugees and applicants for temporary protection, according to statistics, in Poland, Germany, the Czech Republic, Italy, Spain, Romania, France, and the United Kingdom. According to UNHCR Statistics, there are 128,618 thousand Ukrainian refugees in Romania (UNHCR Romania, 2023).

Looking at the statistics, we can see that Ukrainian refugees are found in most member states of the European Union, especially in the countries bordering Ukraine, which indicates a rather strong tendency among them not to emigrate to more distant states, hoping, perhaps, to return as soon as possible to their own country and to the families left behind.

Although we tend to say that migration towards the member states of the European Union is in a significant decline, based on statistics, we must bear in mind that the conflict that created this humanitarian crisis is in full swing. In addition, based on relevant sources of information on the conflict in Ukraine, we can see that Russian attacks on critical infrastructure and civilian areas have not stopped, which could at any time lead to a new escalation of migration to Europe. In this regard, we believe that a multidimensional political and decision-making approach is needed on the part of the member states and, implicitly, of the European Union to achieve policies aimed at managing a future wave of refugees in an efficient and fair manner.

Analysis of the security dimension in Romania

Within this framework, we propose an exhaustive assessment of the effects of the 2022 Ukrainian refugee crisis on security in Romania, with emphasis on the analysis of the impact on various dimensions of Romanian national security. This section aims to identify in a concrete way what are the implications of this migration phenomenon, while providing insight into the political and governmental responses offered to this crisis. By examining the impact of the Ukrainian refugee crisis, we are looking at how this situation has led to significant changes in the security dimension in Romania. Below we will briefly provide an insight into how the Romanian Government has addressed this humanitarian crisis through management policies.

Romania's response to the Ukrainian refugee crisis. In order to respond effectively to the humanitarian crisis created by the war in Ukraine and to succeed in coordinating such a migration phenomenon, the Romanian Government has set up two working groups: a high-level decision-making one, coordinated by the Prime Minister, and an operational one, subordinated to the Head of the Chancellor of the Prime Minister, the latter having as main purpose the coordination and supervision of the activities of ministries in this area. A third group established by the Romanian Government was the Strategic Coordination Group for Humanitarian Assistance, which dealt with ensuring the strategic humanitarian response framework.

The Romanian Government's response to the refugee crisis included providing emergency assistance to refugees entering our country through the crossing points from the North and East of the country, which consisted of providing food, shelter, and medical aid, and organizing humanitarian transports to Ukraine. The second response was to provide protection to those who requested,

through the mechanism for ensuring protection and inclusion measures in the medium and long term. In addition to these safety measures, the Romanian Government activated a civil protection mechanism, through the Department for Emergency Situations, creating 1297 refugee camps or centers in areas bordering the points of entry into the country from Ukraine. In addition, they carried out a series of humanitarian transports and reception of refugees from Ukraine (Chancellery of the Prime Minister, 2022). These measures on providing protection and humanitarian support were accompanied by a series of legislative projects to support people coming from Ukraine and applying for asylum seeker status and granted the right to work to Ukrainian citizens for a period of nine months, initially.

The impact of the refugee crisis on security dimensions. Among the main dimensions of security that have been significantly affected by the 2022 Ukrainian refugee crisis is Romania's economic dimension. The impact of the humanitarian crisis on the economic dimension has been quite extensive, with consequences in several sub-areas of it. Among the most affected economic areas are the national budget, the labor market, external trade, and industry.

The Ukrainian refugee crisis had a major impact on Romania's national budget, with the Government spending about 150 million euro in a year of humanitarian crisis, providing emergency assistance and safety measures to Ukrainian refugees, most of the money allocated being used for receiving, accommodating, and feeding refugees. Moreover, the Romanian Government was forced to reallocate funds and approve budget supplements to ensure social, healthcare, and educational services. Through all these budget relocations, certain areas such as infrastructure and R&D investments have suffered budgetary cuts.

The labor market has also been negatively impacted. The arrival of a significant number of Ukrainian refugees has led to an increase in demand for jobs in particular fields, which generated additional competition and pressure on existing employment resources. In some areas, this increase in demand for labor from Ukrainian refugees created a drop in wages and further discontent within the Romanian population, visibly affected by two previous and quite recent events: the Covid-19 pandemic and the increase in the inflation rate. It is also important to note that the impact on economic security varied across sectors of the economy, with some industries and branches, such as construction and agriculture, benefiting from refugee labor.

A similar impact was exerted on the political and military dimension of Romania's security. This crisis also posed unprecedented threats to Romania's border security. A direct consequence of the flow of Ukrainian refugees into Romania is the pressure exerted on the borders, on the infrastructure in the border counties and on the country's resources. Romanian institutions, aiming to ensure both the country's military and political security, to protect national sovereignty and maintain public order, faced a threat on the Northern and Eastern borders. To succeed in ensuring first border security and, at the same time, efficient management, approximately 5,000 employees of the Ministry of Internal Affairs were deployed at the ten points of entry into the country, with the aim of maintaining national security. Together with 123 agents from the European Union institution, FRONTEX, they acted to combat crimes of trafficking in human beings (Chancellery of the Prime Minister, 2022: 8).

As far as the security of the political dimension is concerned, it has been visibly affected by an increase in skepticism among the population and by amplifying the political tensions created among the Romanian political class. The aid provided to Ukrainian refugees by Romania's current government fuels nationalist parties and their leaders' narratives. For example, the leader of the Alliance for the Unity of Romanians (AUR), the main nationalist party in Romania, repeatedly challenged measures to allocate funds to refugees, noting that most refugees have left Romania. Moreover, several AUR

politicians brought up for discussion historical issues regarding the Romanian minority in Ukraine and its treatment by Ukraine, suggesting in this regard that Romanian institutions should treat Ukrainian refugees in the same way.

With respect to the security of the societal dimension, we believe there is an impact on it, but not as visible as in previous refugee crises, where large numbers of refugees have created social tensions between them and the national population. The explanation for this situation is related to the sharing of a common Eastern European identity, through which we also share the same religion with them, the Orthodox one. Although there have been no public, or at least visible, reactions regarding Ukrainian refugees, according to the most recent Eurobarometer survey, only 62% of Romanians support Ukraine.

Conclusions

Starting from the statistical data used in this paper and observing the large number of refugees who have left Ukraine since the beginning of the military conflict in February 2022, we can conclude that the migration phenomenon in general, and international migration in particular, has become an increasingly common concern on the internal agendas of European states and, of course, a priority in terms of policies on the security of the European Union. We believe that this phenomenon is a priority both for states and for European institutions and international organizations because it represents a security problem for both destination and origin states.

Following the analysis carried out on the security dimensions in Romania, we notice that such a complex and sizeable migration phenomenon, in terms of the number of refugees who entered Romania, affects all dimensions of a state's security and creates a special relationship between the political, military, economic, and societal dimensions, in such a way that managing such an event requires a multidimensional involvement. Although, following the analysis carried out in this paper, we can state that a crisis of this magnitude has mostly a negative impact on Romania's security, we can also identify some positive aspects. Romania's involvement in managing the Ukrainian refugee crisis as a frontline actor has created the opportunity to strengthen certain bilateral and regional relationships and, at the same time, demonstrated that the Romanian state is an extremely important actor for the European Union in terms of European security and external border security.

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